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Anthropology and Psychoanalysis in Ernesto de Martino’s Ethnopsychiatry¹

Abstract: *This paper aims to understand how Ernesto de Martino’s work became the epistemological basis of ethnopsychiatry in Italy, especially through the dialogue between anthropology and psychoanalysis. Demartinian theory can be considered as a foundation for cultural readings of subjectivity and ways of expressing and managing psychological suffering. In this article, I will analyze some of his publications regarding the mythical-ritual aspects of the Italian South (Meridionalist trilogy), specifically his book entitled “La terra del rimorso” (The Land of Remorse), published in 1961. De Martino is not only recognized for his historical contributions to ethnopsychiatry and transcultural psychiatry, but also as a forerunner in the Italian context of what I call a “decolonization of mental health”.*

Keywords: *Ernesto de Martino; ethnopsychiatry; anthropology; psychoanalysis.*

De Martino and the Epistemological Basis of Italian Ethnopsychiatry

My aim here is to understand how Ernesto de Martino can be considered the foundation of Italian ethnopsychiatry for developing some theories about the relationship between culture and subjectivity, the mythical-ritual apparatus and psychopathology. It is not my intention to carry out a hermeneutic of his works and theories, but to identify how they contribute to interpreting subjective suffering from an (ethno)psychoanalytic and cultural perspective. Following a theoretical discussion

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on this subject, I will analyze his ethnographic research published in 1961 (de Martino, [1961b] 2023), which is central to this paper.²

Anthropology and psychoanalysis are fundamental themes in de Martino's work and in the elaboration of his ideas on ethnopsychiatry (Bartocci and Prince, 1998). Although he did not call himself an ethnopsychiatrist, there is a great tendency to consider him the first author in this field (Beneduce and Taliani, 2015). After all, his ethnographic research in southern Italy in 1959 was conducted by a transdisciplinary team, including a psychologist, psychiatrist, musicologist, and anthropologist. One of the main concepts and theories is the "crisis of presence" and the resolute and rescue capacity promoted by mythical-ritual practice. In this sense, authors such as Freud, Jung, and Heidegger were important to him.

De Martino recognizes Carl Jung and Károly Kérenyi as significant authors for thinking about myth as a "model of the past" for dealing with the present, although he does not align himself with Jung's isolation in the theory of archetypes, possibly because of its unhistorical nature. According to de Martino, Jung would have recognized the symbol as a mediator and bridge between the passage from crisis to reintegration. Heidegger's concept of *Dasein* was fundamental to de Martino's theoretical development, especially when discussing the "crisis of presence." However, I believe that Freud's work is aligned with Heidegger's *Dasein* in de Martino's theory in the following way: "being in the world" is not guaranteed and, therefore, there is a permanent risk of losing oneself. In the Freudian interpretative line, this refers to the risk of an inauthenticity of self, the possibility of becoming mentally ill (the dissociation of the "self").

De Martino entered the ethnopsychiatric field by incorporating psychoanalysis, anthropology, and philosophy in his understanding of culture and the human psyche: the permanent risk of becoming mentally ill by losing oneself. His theory of the mind, suffering and culture concatenated in the idea of the "crisis of presence" is authoritatively aligned with the discussions in the field of mental health of his time. De Martino established a rupture in the interpretation of disorders of the mind and

² Other publications by Ernesto de Martino could be included, such as his texts on the psychopathology of cultural apocalypses (e.g., de Martino 1964, 1977). However, for this paper, I chose his ethnography on tarantism in Southern Italy because it presents important aspects of ritual practice ("loss of presence") as a cultural language for dealing with subjective suffering. This was a fundamental transdisciplinary work for the constitution of the theoretical basis of Italian ethnopsychiatry.

the way subjective pain is managed given the extreme biologism of mid-twentieth-century neurology and psychiatry. This was the beginning of Italian medical anthropology, one could boldly say (*Ibid.*).

The “crisis of presence,” according to de Martino, is the loss of the ability to act according to sociocultural values, as if the subject remained in a state of “inauthenticity of self,” to use a more psychoanalytical conception. In cultural terms, this is a subjective and social paralysis, a repetitive imprisonment of the traumatic or distressing situation. For de Martino, presence in the world is not guaranteed, and the risk of losing it is a constant in human life. Thus, from his ethnography in Southern Italy in 1959 (de Martino, [1961b] 2023), he was able to recognize this existential risk of subjectivity becoming ill as something of human history, and not just a situation of the precariousness of the *Mezzogiorno*. Of course, there is a historical-anthropological basis to his theory that distances him from the religious phenomenology of Mircea Eliade or Jung, given that each historical context defines not only the modalities of the crisis of presence but also its resolving techniques: mythical-ritual, therapeutic, or psychoanalytic, among others.

I would go further in this Demartinian definition of losing the ability to act according to sociocultural values, by adding the idea of the loss of the “ego” as an organizing function, the loss of the self, and the fading of subjectivity. The individual becomes detached from their subjectivity and cannot act according to their desire, falling into a repetitive emptiness of anguish. In this way, the loss of presence is not just an inability to act according to cultural values, but also the loss of the subject’s ability to align themselves with their desire and their language: what speaks in the individual, as if it were a possession (or dis-possession of the self), is another “self” (the suffering that does not go away and repeats itself).

The concept of “loss of presence” can be inserted into a broader debate about psychopathology, about a possible cultural translation of mental illness. According to Demartinian theory, subjective suffering is caused by a traumatic or distressing event, and not by a physiological or genetic illness. Although the author does not rule out the possibility of a biological illness caused by imbalances in the body (by internal or external agents), his research points us in another direction: the possibility of culture and life in society making the subject ill, causing bodily suffering (physical and mental).

The “loss of presence” is understood by de Martino (1961b) as an “irrelative de-historicization,” the very distressing and paralyzing situation that the subject goes through without institutional and ritual support. The other possibility is “institutional de-historicization,” which consists of a technique of cultural control and resolution of subjective pain, such as the rite of tarantism,³ a cultural and ritualistic phenomenon in Southern Italy associated with the bite of a spider. For de Martino, “the risk of ‘not being’ is linked to external conditions and brings with it the possibility of overcoming them” (Pompa, 2022). We cannot understand this idea without first understanding the category of “de-historicization.”

De Martino defends the idea that magical-religious rituals can take the subject out of history, a place of anguish and suffering, where trauma happens. It is not a metaphysical or supernatural reality, but a technical, symbolic-ritual apparatus capable of creating an environment and a narrative in which suffering is resignified (Beneduce and Taliani, 2001; Carignani, 2004; de Martino, [1961b] 2023). The internal conflict thus finds a horizon for naming, managing, and resolving (Pires, 2024). This exit from history (de-historicization) is not definitive during the ritual, as there is a return to social and cultural life, which de Martino (1961b) calls “cultural reintegration.”

In a rite of possession and exorcism, as in the phenomenon of tarantism analyzed by de Martino, ([1961b] 2023), there is a state of loss of self, induced by the ritual (institutional de-historicization), which occurs only in that context. In the end, the subject returns to themselves because they do not remain possessed all the time. In this way, the ritual makes it possible to remove the subject from the place of their pain from a shared and resolute symbolic horizon, bringing the individual back into their history, and making them recover their capacity to act in the society.

It is interesting to note that the loss of presence is a psychopathological risk that is not only found in rural societies, an idea that de Martino took some time to elaborate and which becomes clear in his *La terra del rimorso* (The land of remorse, 1961) and *Furore simbolo valore* (Fury symbol value, 1962). The risk of becoming disconnected

³ Tarantism is an Italian cultural and ritual phenomenon in which a person manifests symptoms of possession and trance following the real-symbolic bite of a poisonous spider. The “exorcism” of these people (*tarantati*) is performed by a band playing musical instruments, and the *tarantato* (the person bitten by the spider) may dance for hours and days.

from oneself and the world and the fading of the power to act has occurred in both the past and the present of different societies, marked by their historical specificities. However, de Martino does not remain in this tragic position of subjective sickening and the ever-present risk of the fragmentation of the self.

Just as the loss of presence accompanies sociocultural and historically determined situations, the techniques for rescuing this imminent crisis follow the same path. For de Martino, there is an external cause (historical, sociocultural) located in the traumatic situation that impacts subjectivity in different ways, paralyzing or eliminating “presence.” In this sense, he identifies magical-religious rituals as a technique for culturally rescuing this risk of nonbeing (subjective illness), a cultural language for suffering and, as such, marked by its historicity. His dialogue with anthropology and psychoanalysis is deeply marked by a historical perspective.

Ernesto de Martino’s importance in the field of ethnopsychiatry lies in his epistemological break with the understanding of mental disorders as exclusively biogenetic products (Bartocci and Prince, 1998; Beneduce, 2007; Pires, 2023). In addition, he elaborated a cultural theory of subjectivity, suffering, and ways of dealing with it (Beneduce and Taliani, 2015). The figure of the “madman” or schizophrenic, to use a psychiatric term, is constituted as someone who has escaped from what is considered normal within a sociocultural code. The subject who possesses this “split mind” (*schizo* = split, *phrenia* = mind) is someone unable to act according to the values established by culture and the subjective language of each individual. In his dialogue with Pierre Janet during the 1940s,

de Martino revived from oblivion the French school of “dynamic psychology” founded by Pierre Janet, for whom the person is not a substantial being characterized by aptitudes and functions, but a “dynamic” form, that is, a set of interdependent conducts, hierarchized according to a scale of energy levels: from the most automatic to the most conscious. This conception allowed him to distinguish different degrees of “feeling of the real” to imagine a plurality of successive or simultaneous “psychological existences” and to formulate, through this theater of primary and secondary personalities, an early version of the conceptual pair “presence/loss of presence.” (Charuty, 2015, “The Sick Live Their Own Apocalypse”)

The history of culture would be the history of the languages through which subjects reinvent themselves and ensure their presence in the world. This psychopathological risk, found in different societies

throughout history, takes on different forms of manifestation and resolution. In this sense, magical-religious rituals are understood by de Martino as cultural techniques for managing suffering and the risk of the mind becoming ill (Carignani, 2004; de Martino, [1961b] 2023). The rite is capable of incorporating anguish and trauma into its narrative, shifting them to a resolute symbolic horizon (Pires, 2020; 2024). Human pain would find in ritual not only a cultural-historical meaning, but also the possibility of being undone, of passing away, and of recovering the disturbed presence.

In this way, culture is understood as a nominative and resolute possibility for subjective suffering, rather than a singular carapace for the disorders defined by psychiatric discourse (Beneduce, 2007). There is a rupture in the way mental disorders are interpreted, escaping from the psychiatric biologism of the time toward psychopathology. The autonomy and depathologization of some cultural phenomena, such as tarantism, appeared in de Martino's work long before *DSM-III* (1980), *DSM-IV* (1994), and *DSM-V* (2013), which gradually incorporated cultural discussions into the nosography of mental disorders (Pires, 2023; 2024). De Martino broadened the boundaries between the normal and the pathological, understanding the phenomenon of tarantism no longer as a pathology caused by a venomous animal but as a resolute symbolic-ritual horizon, a cultural language for suffering.

Jervis argues that tarantism cannot be explained within psychiatric nosography. In the ethnographic context analyzed by him and de Martino, there was another way of living and interpreting reality that cannot be reduced to an idea of "primitive mentality" (Jervis, [1961] 2023: 315-16). The symptoms of the *tarantati* – individuals under the influence of tarantism (also *tarantata* or *tarantato* in the feminine or masculine singular forms of the noun in Italian) – were close to some diagnoses of delirium, psychosis, or neurosis. However, they took on modes of subjective suffering and symbolic-ritual resolution that could only be understood within that historicity and that cultural apparatus. Suffering is universal, but the languages used to handle pain are historical and cultural. Any universalist reductionism on the part of the psychiatry of the time, according to Jervis, (Ibid., 316), would be insufficient to understand the specificity of this phenomenon:

The hypothesis that the *tarantati* are preferentially subjects of low intelligence and low culture compared to the average population has little value so long as statistical confirmation is lacking; the high number of illiterates among them is not necessarily significant since the cases studied are few concerning a region where illiteracy is high. For the same

reasons, the data collected so far are not such as to substantiate the hypothesis that tarantism groups individuals predisposed to constitutional psychopathies or nervous diseases.... Tarantism is a phenomenon with multifaceted aspects, which cannot be resolved in exclusively psychiatric terms; its future study can probably be continued only on the basis of interdisciplinary convergence.

De Martino's importance to the field of Italian and European ethnopsychiatry lies in his capacity for historical-anthropological and psychoanalytical understanding of cultural phenomena that had previously been interpreted as physiological or exclusively psychiatric pathologies. As well as working with psychiatrist Giovanni Jervis on his ethnographic expedition to southern Italy, de Martino also chose a psychologist, Letizia Jervis Comba, to form part of his transdisciplinary research.

Using the Rorschach psychological test, Comba found that although this type of test can be used in a variety of cultural contexts, it lacks a conceptual and symbolic translation tool. Applying a test developed for a particular white European society in a diverse cultural context can be risky when trying to interpret the causes of subjective suffering. This diversity can even appear within the country in which the test was constructed. When discussing the Rorschach methodology, Comba ([1961] 2023: 339) states that "numerous experimental studies show us how even within one culture, even within one society, situations exist or can be created, which can lead to different paths that reflect on the results."

Regarding the results obtained with the Rorschach test, "they are rather reactions to a situation that does not have the same meaning for those living in a different existential context from the one in which the test was studied" (Ibid., 340). In this way, Comba supports one of the core ideas of Demartinian ethnopsychiatry: the cultural specificity and symbolic autonomy of ritual and its ability to resolve suffering, a technique for recovering presence and reinsertion into history.

One of the great contributions of *La terra del rimorso* (1961) to ethnopsychiatry was its ability to depathologize a legitimate and creative cultural practice, appropriated in southern Italy as a tool for managing existence and psychological suffering (Castelnuovo and Risso, 1982; Risso and Böker, [1964] 2000). De Martino's ethnography questioned the universality of the methods and diagnoses of psychiatry at the time, characterized by a markedly biological and genetic interpreta-

tion of mental disorders. Culture, then, was not a social mask for a universal diagnosis such as schizophrenia or other psychoses. It was understood as a legitimate way of naming, through its own grammar, and managing subjective pain in a metahistorical and ritualistic context where the cause of anguish is given an interpretative and resolute horizon (Beneduce, 2019; Pires, 2023; 2024). The “decolonial” tone of his approach in the field of mental health lies precisely in this perspective that decentralizes the hegemony and sovereignty of the official knowledge of psychiatry (read Western European and Anglo-Saxon), opening the way for other modalities of healing and psychic manifestations (Beneduce and Taliani, 2015; Pires, 2023; Zinn, 2015).

It is interesting to observe, however, that de Martino does not fall into absolute cultural relativism. There is a dialogue, a mediation, between the established knowledge of psychiatry, anthropology and psychoanalysis, and the specificities of cultural languages. There is no dichotomy between these two dimensions, just as there is no absolute separation between “high” and “low” culture. De Martino deconstructs these polarizations in favor of an unequal circularity without hierarchies of value, recognizing in the rural culture of southern Italy a space of resistance and existential creativity (Cannarsa, 1992; Dei, 2023).

The medical discourse of pathologizing subaltern culture, or not recognizing it as a legitimate way of dealing with suffering, is a question of class and power. The folklore and ritual narrative of the Italian South in the mid-twentieth century was erased or left out of scientific studies. The failure to recognize the power of culture (in this case of the rural South) in addressing human suffering presupposes a hierarchization and exclusion of everything that was not legitimized as an effective method capable of healing, namely psychiatry and gradually psychology.

Although it was a legitimate strategy, de Martino ([1961b] 2023) and his team knew that tarantism would soon come to an end and that other forms of healing and management of suffering would be needed. In this way, there is a recognition in his theory of the legitimacy of subaltern cultures as a creative and effective way of coping with pain, but at the same time, there was an idealized project of providing the population of the Mezzogiorno with better social and cultural conditions and alternatives for managing psychic suffering (Beneduce and Taliani, 2015; Gallini, 2005). De Martino did not exclude the importance of psy-

chiatry, psychoanalysis, and psychology in the process of treating subjective suffering; however, he believed that there should be a nonethnocentric and nonhierarchical mediation of this knowledge.

Ernesto de Martino's work is vast, and his southern trilogy – *Sud e magia* (South and magic); *Morte e pianto rituale* (Death and ritual mourning); and *La terra del rimorso* – addresses many of the themes I analyzed earlier, making him a forerunner of ethnopsychiatric theory in Italy. However, I believe that the transdisciplinary ethnography carried out by him and his team in Southern Italy in 1959, concatenated in *La terra del rimorso*, is the most emblematic and important for the discussion of this article. For this reason, I have chosen this research, published in 1961, as the main document of analysis below, bearing in mind the limits that this choice implies regarding the amplitude of de Martino's theory and intellectual trajectory.

The Land of Remorse and Bites: Case Studies with the *Tarantati*

In the winter of 1959, Ernesto de Martino and his transdisciplinary team prepared an ethnography to be carried out in Southern Italy in June of the same year, during the days when the tarantism ritual would take place in the chapel. There was, however, a central question to be investigated: was this ritual an autonomous cultural and symbolic phenomenon or the physical manifestation of a disease caused by the bite of an arachnid? This medical hypothesis has permeated the history of tarantism since the Renaissance: “In the literature on tarantism, from the seventeenth century onward, the *medical* interpretation stood in the foreground, according to which it was a *disease*, to be attributed either to a toxic syndrome from a poisonous arachnid bite or to a psychic disturbance dependent or independent of arachnidism” (de Martino, [1961b] 2023: 23). The second hypothesis was confirmed throughout the research and its results, as I will explore throughout this topic.

The team formed by de Martino was fundamental in investigating the complexity of the phenomenon of tarantism beyond the pathologization of medical discourse. One of the members was Giovanni Jervis, a doctor specializing in clinical neuropsychiatry at the University of Rome. The team also included a psychologist, Letizia Jervis Comba, who in 1956 obtained her master's degree from the Department of Psychology at Cornell University. Although he was not part of the group, Doctor Sergio Bettini, from the Higher Institute of Health, was an important consultant on the toxic syndrome caused by the bite of the

Latrodectus tredecim guttatus. To analyze the musical aspect of tarantism, de Martino invited the ethnomusicologist Diego Carpitella. He also asked the anthropologist Amalia Signorelli-D'Ayala to contribute to the discussion in the field of cultural anthropology (Ibid., 23-24).

Between June 28 and 30, 1959, during the days of the festive celebration in Galatina, in the province of Lecce in Puglia, the team identified 35 *tarantati*, 19 of whom were visited successively in their hometowns. Two cases were subsequently added. De Martino (Ibid., 37) wanted to prove or disprove the medical hypothesis about this phenomenon, which consisted of “limiting tarantism to a form of arachnidism and reducing it to a psychological disorder.”

Tarantism is a cultural phenomenon that circulated in the European and Mediterranean world since medieval times, changing throughout modern history (Ibid.; Pompa, 2022). The diachronic aspects of this ritual are explored by de Martino, but will not be the focus of my investigation, which seeks to understand the anthropological and psychoanalytical interpretation of this case and not its historical genealogy. What the researchers witnessed in 1959 in Southern Italy was a remnant of this cultural practice, adapted to local specificities and the historicity of the time. It was a rite in decline, about to disappear, as the team identified at the beginning of the ethnography. Throughout modern times, this phenomenon was interpreted from a medical and biological perspective, in which the symptoms presented by the *tarantati* were the consequence of the actual bite of a poisonous arachnid. The etymology of tarantism comes from the name “tarantula” for the venomous animal, the material and symbolic root of a narrative that de Martino and his team identified as something far beyond (psycho)pathology.

The physiological explanation defended by most doctors and scholars is concatenated in the definition of “toxic latrodectism syndrome.” After being bitten by an arachnid of the genus *Latrodectus*, the subject experiences symptoms of an altered mental state, subjective suffering, pain, and other physical consequences:

the crisis of tarantism approximately mimicked the toxic syndrome of latrodectism.... The falling to the ground, the sense of exhaustion, the anguish, the state of psychomotor agitation with obnubilation of the sensorium, the difficulty of keeping upright, the stomachache, nausea, and vomiting, the various paresthesias and muscular pains, the exaltation of the venereal appetite.... (de Martino, [1961b] 2023: 46)

This explanation was the most widely accepted during modern times and even when de Martino began his ethnography in Puglia. He

and his team suspected, however, that something from the symbolic field was involved in this apparently pathological phenomenon. Given the long biological and positivist tradition of medicine and psychiatry, it was not surprising that tarantism was considered exclusively a disease caused by a *Latrodectus*.

Tarantism occurred during the summer, between May and August. Exactly at harvest time and during the intense work in the fields. This was when the “first bite” occurred, and from that moment on, the symptoms of the “bite” were repeated constantly and seasonally during the same period. For example, a person bitten in July or August would show symptoms during the summer; the following year, the same symptoms would recur, repeating the behaviors and intensity of the physical and subjective suffering. Through this and other findings, de Martino (Ibid., 40) began to suspect that it was not just something to do with the physiology of the spider bite:

the toxic syndrome from the bite of *Latrodectus tredecim guttatus* was absolutely incompatible with the recurrence of the crisis for dozens of years. Instead, this repetition, so characteristic of tarantism, hinted at cultural conditioning, respect for a tradition, the seasonal repetition of a rite, the calendrical celebration of a ceremony.

The author’s question arises from the repetition of the symptoms of tarantism. How could the symptoms caused by the “first bite” be repeated every year? Every summer, the anguish, delirium, loss of self, and states of agitation and fainting return. All this is repeated in the same summer context for years and decades. Every summer, a “re-bite” (*ri-morso*). In Italian, *rimorso* means re-bite or remorse. Both represent a subjective state and a symbolic action of tarantism on the body. Gradually, de Martino (Ibid., 46) came to the conclusion that tarantism had a symbolic autonomy and could not be reduced to a disease caused by the poisoning of a tarantula, “escaping any attempt to ‘naturalistically reduce’ tarantism to a somatic or psychic illness.” However, this cultural phenomenon was connected to the narrative of physiological illness, caused by the actual bite of the *Latrodectus tredecim guttatus* or another venomous animal.

Among the many cases analyzed by Ernesto de Martino and his team, I have selected three that offer an in-depth view of tarantism, based on the biography and suffering of these individuals: Maria di Nardò, Filomena di Cerfignano, and Pietro di Nardò. From these cases, it will be possible to understand the family, subjective, sociocultural,

and psychic aspects of the plot that made up tarantism, that is, how tarantism was constituted as a horizon for resolving and accommodating the mental suffering of those subjects.

Maria di Nardò

The first case concerns Maria di Nardò, a *tarantata* who worked in the tobacco harvest and in the fields. She was married for nine years to a peasant. Orphaned by her father 13 years ago, she was taken to her aunt and uncle's house and had little contact with her mother. De Martino reports that Maria di Nardò spent her adolescence in constant anguish due to this situation of non-place and contempt from her family. When she was 18, she fell in love with a young man; however, for financial reasons, his family opposed the marriage, and he left her. "Maria suffered greatly from this abandonment because she was in her first love: and so 'one Sunday at noon' she was bitten by the tarantula while at the window and was forced to dance" (Ibid., 70).

The mother of another boy considered Maria de Nardò to be a good partner for her unemployed and sick son, even though she was a *tarantata*. This title did not carry good connotations in that society, as it meant someone who showed a certain emotional instability. The mother asked Maria if she would like to marry her son, but "still having her first love in her heart, [Maria] did not utter a word, and to take her time she made the excuse that she had no money for the trousseau because of the tarantula, which forced her to dance and continually run up debts with the musicians" (Ibid., 71). As mother and son continued to insist with their marriage proposal, "a new character, St. Paul, came on the scene, who appeared to Maria and commanded her not to marry, calling her to a mystical wedding with him" (Ibid.).

In order to advance the situation and the proposal, the mother and son sent a woman to Maria's house and invite her to talk to them. Maria was taken out of town, where they were waiting for her and proposed that she live with her potential husband for a while to see how the situation would develop. Maria accepted this request and, after a while, when her partner addressed her in a rude tone asking her to iron the bed linen, they fought. After this event, Maria met St. Peter and St. Paul in her "vision" and they both said to her: "Leave the iron behind and come with us." She replied: "And who do I leave my husband with?" The saints responded: "Don't worry about your husband" (Ibid.). The situation continued as follows:

It was on a Sunday, at noon, the very same day and hour when she had first been bitten by the tarantula and received her first call from St. Paul.

Maria, after wandering around the fields for three days, returned to her parents: St. Paul, displeased with her for disobeying his order not to marry, let her be bitten a second time, forcing her to dance for nine days. Meanwhile, the whole neighborhood knew that she had been in the farmhouse with the young man, and to repair the misdeed it was now necessary to get married, even if it was unwelcome to her and the saint. The conflict thus came to a compromise: Maria consented to the wedding to the new suitor – that is, to her current husband – but at the same time maintained her seasonal relationship with the tarantula and the saint, renewing the crisis and the dance every year, with a marked preference for the warm months, for the menstrual period and the approach of the Galatina festival. (Ibid., 71-72)

The St. Paul element is interpreted by de Martino as a sublimated figure of unfulfilled first love. We can also understand the vision with the saint as a Super-egoic self-punishment for the nonfulfillment of Maria's desire or, on the contrary, as the radical expression of her unrealized desire. St. Paul's order not to marry her current husband symbolizes, on the narrative level of tarantism, a deep unfulfilled desire, resulting in the punishment of dancing for nine days. However, this is not just a symbolization of an unsatisfied will, but an operation to resolve the situation and the anguish felt by Maria di Nardò. Maria's psychic conflict is accommodated in the ritual repetition of tarantism, finding meaning and a horizon of resolution in it.

The repression of desire creates a constant psychic conflict, generating a symptom that found meaning and resolution in the ritual of tarantism, not just because of the scarcity of languages for pain, but as an authentic and creative way of elaborating suffering through the cultural grammar present at that time. Thus, by marrying a man she did not love, "Maria continued periodically to pay her tribute to the tarantula and the saint, each time reciting in the symbolism of the ritual the story of the love bite" (Ibid., 72). The resolute operation, according to de Martino (Ibid.), took place

in the mythical-ritual horizon of tarantism – and of the Christian grafting of the figure of St. Paul – Maria periodically released her conflicting energies and symbolically enacted her frustrations, thus relieving the interceremonial periods, that is, daily life, from the burden of unconscious tensions that would have been extremely dangerous if she had not found in tarantism a socialized and traditionalized framework for calendrical and festive treatment. Through the mythical order of "tarantula," "bite," "poison," and St. Paul, Maria gave shape to conflicting and frustrating psychic content.

Through tarantism, Maria managed her subjective conflicts, creating a way of dealing with the fact that she had married unwillingly and had to endure the presence of her husband and the absence of her family. Her anguish was displaced into a resolving ritual circumstance, in a cathartic and symbolizing way. It was resolute not as a total cure or disappearance of symptoms, but as a therapeutic and soothing function, as de Martino mentions. In other words, it was a way of seeing her pain publicly recognized, resolved collectively by the gaze of others and by the expulsion of her suffering through the musical exorcism of tarantism:

At the same time, Maria channeled her aggressive energy against her unwelcome husband in an alienated form, putting a strain on marital life, financially harming the unloved family, and clamorously calling attention to her personal drama from people who normally did not pay attention to her....

Among other things, the case of Maria di Nardò highlighted how tarantism provided a symbolic device for a conflicting psychic content, which had found no resolution on the level of consciousness, and which operated in the darkness of the unconscious, risking being asserted as a neurotic symbol. It was evoked and configured on the mythical-ritual plane. There, it could be periodically discharged and enacted, relieving the interceremonial periods of its stresses, and facilitating a relative psychic equilibrium during those periods. (Ibid., 72-73)

Although this was not the only example they investigated, the case of Maria di Nardò was one of the most complete in biographical, anthropological, and psychoanalytical terms, with the greatest possibilities for interpretation. Its qualitative and ethnographic material allowed us to visualize the hypotheses of de Martino and his team. The next shorter analyses will illustrate other sides of the complex subjective and cultural phenomenon of tarantism.

Filomena di Cerfignano

On June 24, 1959, just before de Martino's team left for the town of Nardò, they observed an interesting case in the St. Paul's chapel in Galatina concerning tarantism's symbolic autonomy. It was a 71-year-old peasant woman called Filomena di Cerfignano, who was sitting at the altar on a bunch of chickpeas, ceremonially repeating the disaster that had befallen her:

Filomena lamented her aching abdomen, legs, kidneys, head, and precordial oppression – using the mimetic modes and melodic structure of Cerfignano's funeral lament – and scattered her lament with invocations

to St. Paul: “My beautiful saint, grant me mercy! I have done nothing to you! Do not use poison one more time!” (Ibid., 74)

Filomena told the team, as confirmed by her daughter and her husband, that it was a first-bite episode, which took place in front of the couple’s house. Five days earlier, at midday, she had fought with her husband while she was collecting chickpeas from a branch, which she had placed at her feet when she was in the chapel. Just then, a spider bit her. Filomena saw the animal slide down her legs, and when she got home, she saw the green arachnid on the bed, the same one that had bitten her a short time before. There was not enough time for the spider to take off into the house on the bed, but her husband confirmed that this type of animal “flies like the wind” and is capable of such speed and agility. De Martino asked her why she had not killed the spider. Filomena replied that it was “a creature of St. Paul” and that killing it would be an offense to the saint. Her husband confirmed that the arachnid had been sent by the saint. This case illustrates how important family and cultural narratives are for maintaining the ritual and symbolism of tarantism. An environment, historicity, and sharing are necessary. The pain was resignified collectively.

The same day she was bitten, Filomena went to St. Paul’s chapel, as she knew she was in a frightened state. The visit had no effect. According to a baptismal godmother who was there, the cure would only come if Filomena dressed as she had when she was bitten, bringing with her the object that had been found at the scene of the bite (in this case, the bunch of chickpeas she had been carrying). Filomena went back to the house to follow the instructions of the lady from Galatina and returned to the chapel soon after. Her husband reported the following about the episode of the bite and the symptoms of his *tarantata* wife:

The husband explained that his wife had not been bitten by a “dancing” or “singing” or “libertine” tarantula and therefore did not dance, did not feel stimulated by joyful songs, and did not indulge in lascivious mimicry: it was simply a “sad and mute” tarantula that disdained the rhythm of the tarantella folk dance and induced in its victim a melancholic mood, which could at most be expressed through a funeral lament. (Ibid., 75)

The spider represents, within the unique narrative of tarantism, the symptom that the victim suffers and from which she must rid herself through musical exorcism, performed by the paid community band. In Filomena’s case, these were sadness, melancholy, and the inability to

speak. These symptoms, however, are located within the subject's trajectory and through a traumatic or distressing situation that has not been resolved psychically, inaugurated in the scene of the "first bite." The psychic conflict, in this case, was not explored as much due to the lack of information gathered during the interview with Filomena. The only clue was the fight with her husband, which was probably linked to problems, repressions, and anguish in her marital or family life.

As de Martino (1961b) concluded, it is interesting to observe that the language used to express and elaborate Filomena's suffering existed within the shared grammar of tarantism, constituting what he calls the "symbolic autonomy of the ritual." Going to St Paul's chapel without the objects and clothes she had been carrying when she was first bitten had no therapeutic or calming effect. Although the team does not exclude the real presence of the bite and the arachnid, the process of resolution and elaboration of the pain follows different paths, autonomous from the reality of latroductism.

Pietro di Nardò

On July 5, 1959, the team visited Pietro di Nardò on a farm. Pietro was a 50-year-old farmer who was bitten at night while sleeping in 1955. The doctor at the Nardò hospital said it was a real case of latroductism: "the patient presented with psychomotor agitation with sensory obnubilation, extremely violent pain in the head, widespread pain in the whole body and limbs, pronounced painful rigidity of muscle masses, conjunctival hyperemia, and urinary retention that lasted for two days" (Ibid., 76). He was the only real victim of *latroductus toxicus* syndrome caused by arachnid venom, but even in his case the symbolic autonomy of tarantism was present.

After having been bitten by the arachnid in 1955, Pietro visualized the spider and began to repeat bodily movements following the traditional model of tarantism. Pietro became a publicly recognized *tarantato*, dancing to the sound of the musical exorcism and the colors presented to him. The ritual narrative is made up of a specific symbolic and corporeal apparatus, but also of a collective and individual recognition of being "possessed" or "commanded" by the "spider entity" responsible for the first bite (in this case, real and symbolic at the same time). De Martino (Ibid.) reports:

Discharged from the hospital in Nardò, where he had been admitted, and despite this diagnosis, he had now become a *tarantato*, stimulated by music, dance, and colors. In fact, he danced for four days, to the

sound of the tarantella, while the audience threw ribbons of various colors at him “for proof”: but Pietro wanted a multicolored rag, and wrapped his head with it, like a turban.

Pietro’s crises occurred in and out of the typical season of tarantism (summer). However, there was always an element that provoked this altered state of consecutive dancing, whether it was sound or colors. One day, when he went to the barber-violinist in his town, he had another crisis, caused by someone playing the guitar. It is unknown whether it was out of malice or just an accident. From then on, Pietro began to show movements of the traditional dance of the *tarantati*. He was taken to the house, where he asked for the musicians (those responsible for playing the songs that made the *tarantati* dance and free themselves):

In fact, the group of players arrived from Nardò, led by the barber-violinist. Pietro indulged wildly in the dance: he went dancing through the fields, on the ground, or on his feet, followed by the group of players who tried as best they could to discipline this frenzy with rhythm, and to prevent their client from falling into some ditch and hurting himself. In January ’56, still out of season, another crisis and another dance. Then nothing more, until this year. The crisis had occurred just two days before our visit, roughly corresponding to the time of the “first bite,” in the right season, according to all the rules of tarantism. (Ibid., 77)

In addition to the dance and the musical exorcism, the figure of St. Paul was also present in Pietro’s imagination. His relationship with the saint consisted of a search for healing, to expel the interference of the “tarantula” in his life. The saint, however, forced Pietro to dance for hours and days, threatening him if he did not follow his orders. De Martino (Ibid., 78) reports:

Once the saint ordered him to dance “until noon” and to go to the chapel in Galatina the next day: in fact, at the tolling of the noon bell, Pietro stopped dancing, but since he did not feel like going to Galatina the next day, because of the great fatigue that usually follows dancing, the implacable saint threatened him, “I’m waiting for you: if you don’t come, the worst is yours.” Pietro and his family (his wife, three daughters, and sister) reported these facts to us, showing a certain resentment toward the tarantula, which forced its victims to such eccentric behavior and unbalanced the family budget with heavy spending.

Pietro’s subjective suffering, however, is not clear from the accounts collected by de Martino’s team. However, there is a clue in the passage quoted above that points to some interpretative directions: the existence of a tarantula entity that forced a family man to behave like

this and obey its movements and characteristics. To do what was not socially authorized, to break with what limited Pietro in his position as a father who must behave: “At one point, while narrating his dance through the fields accompanied by the little orchestra, Pietro commented with a melancholy sigh, ‘But just see what a family man like me gets up to!’” (Ibid.).

Tarantism repositions the psychic suffering that afflicts the subject, moving it into a symbolic narrative where the *tarantato* follows the orders of St. Paul and the spider. In this context of ritual dance and dis(obedience), Pietro let flow what he was not allowed to do as a family man, within that community and historicity. As de Martino reports, unbalancing himself and assuming an eccentric position was at the heart of Pietro’s anguish. The discomfort was probably located in family relationships. The ritual offered, even under the dictates of a possessing entity, a transgression of a forbidden position (getting lost, dancing for hours and days, getting out of his father’s social role). The ritual could move anguish to a symbolic context different from social reality, in which it was possible to identify a therapeutic horizon and a resolution to suffering.

The repression of desire found its possibility of symbolic realization in the ritual within the language of tarantism. In this operation lies the resolute horizon that this cultural phenomenon provided. It was a topic developed, for example, by contemporary ethnopsychiatry in Europe through various approaches. Nevertheless, de Martino and his team opened a space for this debate at the end of the 1950s.

Final Considerations

De Martino was a key author in the development of Italian ethnopsychiatry. The debates listed in this paper present the beginning of the process of incorporating culture as an autonomous and effective language in the management of suffering, without disregarding the validity of and dialogue with the established psy field. In this way, his work initiated, at least in the Italian context, a process of decolonization of psy-knowledge, which was based exclusively on Anglo-Saxon and European psychiatry.

Decolonization, in this case, would be the opening up to other modalities and operations for managing suffering that were not completely aligned with psychiatric manuals and politically legitimized psy theories at a global level. De Martino presented us with a cultural lan-

guage (tarantism) that accommodated the suffering of the subjects participating in this narrative and ritual. Tarantism displaced anguish into a mythical-symbolic field in which the bite of the arachnid and the musical dance-exorcism incorporated a horizon of meaning and resolution of the problem.

De Martino's work became the basis of Italian ethnopsychiatry and transcultural psychiatry from the 1960s onward (Stanghellini and Ciglia, 2013). The most emblematic example was Risso and Böker's ([1964] 2000) *Sortilegio e delirio* (Sorcery and delirium), a study of Southern Italian immigrants in Switzerland who presented symptoms and explanations for their subjective suffering based on the symbolic-cultural reality of the Mezzogiorno: magical works, enchantments, possessions, and states of "loss of self." Vittorio Lanternari (2000: 14) states:

It could be said that de Martino opens the way of ethnopsychiatry in Italy at the time when Risso opens that of transcultural psychiatry: and by that I mean that ethnopsychiatry presents itself as that section of anthropological science that opens up to the psychiatric perspective, in order to identify and interpret the relationships between behaviors and collective representations from cognitive and scientific intents.

Working with subjectivity means working with difference, with singularity, with Otherness. De Martino, in his anthropological-psychanalytical approach in dialogue with Gramscian Marxism, believed that change and social equality in southern Italy would bring relief and new ways of dealing with suffering beyond tarantism. If Fanon had an engaged clinic, de Martino proposed an engaged ethnography, a new humanism present in his concept of "critical ethnocentrism." His political and intellectual work began in the 1950s but is still in vogue in contemporary social and clinical discussions, whether in psychiatry or anthropology. This debate is not over, and these authors identified a problem that is still present today: a clinic that is alienated from social changes is very limited.

Recent research has emphasized the importance of the humanities (history, anthropology, sociology) in considering mental health at a global level, as well as how culture and society cross our minds (Antić et al., 2023). This is still a current debate in transdisciplinary studies of the mind, with its roots in the twentieth century. De Martino, as my analysis has shown, was fundamental to the foundation of Italian eth-

nopsychiatry and is closely connected to this debate, which is researched worldwide in transcultural studies of the psyche (Antić et al., 2023; Beneduce, 2005, 2011; Beneduce and Taliani, 2015).

Whether or not Ernesto de Martino was a pioneer in these discussions, locally or globally, was not the aim of this article. However, what I would like to highlight is how, at the end of the 1950s, he developed a historical-anthropological reading of mental suffering and its management, moving away from biologizing psychiatric paradigms that dismissed the role of culture and the psychogenesis of mental disorders. This debate is still in vogue, full of contradictions and open questions.

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